

School-Based Action Research Through the Lens of Elementary Teachers: Promises and Pitfalls

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Abstract. This qualitative-phenomenological study explored the challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of ten teacher-researchers from different public elementary schools of Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur. The participants were chosen through purposive sampling, and their responses were analyzed using Creswell's Thematic Analysis. The study unveiled that teacher-researchers experienced time constraints, lack of financial support, and lack of research skills. Participants' apathy and heavy workloads also hindered them from conducting their research studies smoothly. Despite these challenges, teacher-researchers sought social support networks and balance their administrative workloads simultaneously. They sought professional development and reminded themselves of their skilled and educational motivations. Nonetheless, they believed that even if research was a challenging process, they learned significant values and thought this was beneficial for improving the educational facet. The study recommended that policymakers consider budgetary allocation and equipment support for teacher-researchers. These future research directions could contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with action research, ultimately benefiting educators and students in improving educational practices and outcomes.

KEY WORDS

1. School-based action research 2. teacher-researchers 3. professional development,

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1. Introduction

Action research is an active and intentional method used in education. Teachers use a structured process to address particular issues in their teaching methods. This involves identifying problems, making educated guesses about solutions, and implementing these ideas to improve their classrooms. Essentially, action research gives educators the tools to understand the complexities of their classrooms and work towards practical solutions, thus connecting educational theories with real-world practice. Action research is also when educators create an academic paper based on an identified, existing problem in the educational field and aim to solve such a problem. Integral to this investigative process is the sequential application of pre-test and post-test assessments, serving as methodological benchmarks to ascertain the efficacy of the implemented intervention within the targeted sample or demographic cohort. While

the pursuit is deemed beneficial and professionally gratifying, teachers undoubtedly encounter challenges along the conduct of their study, perhaps in resources and finances to support their study, research participants, and other stakeholders pivotal to this endeavor such study and others. Historically, the term “action research” has long been associated with the work of Kurt Lewin, who considered the research method cyclical, dynamic, and collaborative. Through repeated planning, observation, and reflection cycles, individuals and groups engaged in action research can make the necessary changes for society’s betterment. To extend this concept, Kemmis and McTaggart (1988), as cited by Hine (2013), mention that they view action research as a collaborative process carried out by people with common interests—people in the educational facet in this sense. Moreover, these authors posit that action research is a “form of collective reflective inquiry undertaken by participants in social situations to improve the rationality and justice of their own social or educational practices, as well as their understanding of these practices and the situations in which these practices are carried out.” In education, action research involves addressing issues within social systems like schools. The focus is on solving specific problems by creating new knowledge and taking action within the school environment where the problem exists. The aim is to cultivate a collective understanding of problem-solving methods, closing the gap between theory and practice (Bourner Brook, 2019). Action research benefits the professional lives of individuals operating within educational systems. However, doing action research to pursue academic excellence or professional growth is not a walk in the park, as this undertaking necessitates grit, passion, and mission. While one might initially perceive it as promising, this endeavor also harbors distinct pitfalls into which a teacher-researcher may stumble. According to the Organization

for Economic Cooperation and Development (2020), Action Research as part of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) is vital for teachers to broaden and deepen their knowledge, keep up with new research, tools, and practices, and respond to students’ changing needs. It also plays a crucial role in building collaborative school cultures and supporting the collective improvement of the teaching profession. While teachers’ initial education is critical to ensuring that new teachers are prepared for their work, action research under CPD is a piece in the continuum of teachers’ professional growth (Boeskens et al., 2020; Shaik-Abdullah et al., 2020). Alongside these are problems teachers encounter in doing action research. The specific problems faced by teachers in conducting research include lack of time, insufficient funding, heavy workload, complex proposal process, lack of mentorship, poor knowledge in data analysis, lack of knowledge in publishing papers, large class sizes, limited access to research resources, and poor internet connection. In Oman, as Al-Balushi (2022) outlined, English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers across different public schools encounter several hurdles when engaging in classroom action research. These teachers encounter difficulty because their participation is primarily driven by the requirement of action research activities within their teacher preparation programs. Specifically, they grapple with challenges such as a need for a more theoretical understanding of action research, constraints on time, and a lack of intrinsic motivation. In Indonesia, specifically in East Java Indonesia, a survey shows that 84% of teachers in the Philippine context, the DepEd ranking guidelines, specified in DepEd Order No. 66 series of 2007, incorporate research and development projects. These guidelines assign specific points to action research conducted at different educational levels, such as school, district, or division, as outlined in DepEd Memo No. 18 series of 2018. Teachers must participate in research undertak-

ings as an integral component of the Philippines' Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). This system is harmonized with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), highlighting the importance of research and inventive thinking within the teaching field. Educators are proactively motivated to participate in research ventures to refine their teaching methodologies within this structure. However, recent studies in different regions of the country revealed that many teachers struggle to publicize their studies for various reasons. In Quezon City, a comprehensive survey highlights the proficiency levels of 147 elementary and secondary educators across 38 critical skills pertinent to action research composition. The findings reveal that a substantial portion of these teachers, encompassing 32 skills, registered within the lower bracket of competency. Notably, six specific skills fell into the less competent category. Areas of weakness among teacher-researchers include selecting appropriate tools for data analysis and interpretation, encoding both quantitative and qualitative data, and effectively interpreting results derived from software applications. Moreover, a significant deficiency was observed in publishing completed action research endeavors. Beyond skill assessment, factors such as knowledge, attitude, and resource availability were identified as influential determinants impacting educators' involvement in action research endeavors (Oestar Marzo, 2022). In Pangasinan, research conducted in 2022 within the Pangasinan Division II mother high schools revealed the pervasive challenges encountered by secondary teachers in carrying out action research initiatives. These challenges span various dimensions. These are notably financial constraints, time limitations, and bureaucratic procedures enforced by the Division Office, which makes it difficult for teacher-researchers to smoothly implement their research from thesis writing, implementation, and the publications of their study (Abrenica, 2022). More so, other studies in Tuguegarao, Laguna, and other regions in the country have revealed that many teachers struggle in the publication of their studies due to additional heavy workloads, lack of time, anxiety, inadequate knowledge in action research, and financial restrictions (Tindowen, 2019). Bulky teaching loads, limited time and resources, lack of technical and methodological expertise, the dearth of training, and disappointments in the research process are a few of the issues teachers inevitably face as obstacles in doing research. I also observed this concern among teacher-researchers in the Kiblawan South locale, Davao City. Teacher-researchers are grappling with the inception of their individual action research projects and the subsequent requirement for publication. The present study explores teacher-researchers' intricate experiences within public elementary schools encompassing the expanse of Kiblawan South District. Notably, scant scholarly inquiries have been conducted, and the existing body of literature needs to be more extensive in its coverage of this phenomenon (Abrenica Cascolan, 2022; Aguilar-de Borja, 2018). Consequently, this study seeks to make a substantive scholarly contribution by embarking on an exploration within a district situated in the province of Davao del Sur. Through this endeavor, the study seeks to enrich the reservoir of knowledge and facilitate a more comprehensive and nuanced analysis of this phenomenon.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to investigate teacher-researchers' lived experiences in conducting their respective Action Research within the scope of Kiblawan South District public elementary schools. This study intends to gain insights from the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of teacher-researchers regarding the phenomenon being investigated.

1.2. *Research Questions*—The study intended to gain insights and opportunities for teachers engaged in the action research. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What challenges do teacher-researchers encounter in conducting action research?
- (2) What do teacher-researchers employ the coping strategies/mechanisms in conducting their action research?
- (3) What do teacher-researchers learn from the educational insights when conducting their action research?

1.3. *Definition of Terms*—Qualitative-Phenomenological Study: A research approach that seeks to understand individuals' lived experiences and perspectives through in-depth analysis of personal accounts. In this study, it explores the challenges and coping mechanisms of teacher-researchers.

Teacher-Researchers: Educators who engage in academic research alongside their teaching responsibilities. In this study, they are public elementary school teachers conducting action research in Kiblawan South District, Davao del Sur.

Purposive Sampling: A non-random sampling technique where participants are selected based on specific criteria relevant to the research. In this study, ten teacher-researchers were chosen for their experiences with action research.

1.4. *Significant of the Study*—Accordingly, this research study recognizes the teacher-researchers lived experiences in conducting action research. Hence, the study was deemed beneficial for the following: Educational Sector. The research findings would provide insights into challenges and opportunities for teacher researchers in action research. This aids policymakers in customizing professional development opportunities and methodologies. School Heads. The research findings would give school administrators a deeper understanding of teacher-researchers' realities during the action research process. This insight can inform the creation of supportive structures and resources that facilitate and encourage teacher-research

Creswell's Thematic Analysis: A method of qualitative data analysis introduced by John Creswell that involves identifying, analyzing, and reporting themes within the data. This process was used to analyze the teacher-researchers' responses.

Time Constraints: A challenge experienced by teacher-researchers, referring to the lack of sufficient time to conduct research due to other teaching and administrative responsibilities.

Lack of Financial Support: One of the challenges teacher-researchers faced, referring to the limited or nonexistent funds provided to support their research activities.

Research Skills: The specific abilities required to effectively conduct academic research. The lack of these skills was a hindrance for some teacher-researchers in this study.

initiatives. Teacher-Researchers. The research findings would validate teacher-researchers' experiences, acknowledging their challenges and successes. This recognition can inspire a sense of shared camaraderie and provide reassurance that their efforts contribute to advancing educational practices. Students and Parents. The research findings would indirectly benefit students and parents by shedding light on a culture of evidence-based teaching practices for students and greater confidence in the educational system. Future Researchers. This study would provide foundational data to inspire additional research on the subject matter under investigation, particularly for aspiring teacher-researchers.

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—The primary foundation of this study rests upon Edward Thorndike’s Trial and Error Theory (1938). Aligned with Thorndike’s concept, learning takes place through experimentation. This implies that an individual acquires knowledge by attempting various approaches to solve a particular issue. If a method proves ineffective, it is discarded in favor of trying alternative methods until the correct solution is eventually identified. This process enables individuals to eliminate errors and irrelevant paths, ultimately reaching their objective (Gautam, 2018). Additionally, it involves a sequence of attempts a person makes until an accurate response is attained. Analogous to a scientific investigation, the theory concludes existing information, resembling an experiment. In the context of our investigation, participants are actively engaged in conducting their action research, even when faced with potential challenges. They strive to address existing educational problems, progressively uncovering solutions to their queries. Despite obstacles, they are poised to complete their respective studies successfully. Thus, this theory encompasses the challenges teachers encounter and their strategies for overcoming them. Meanwhile, the abovementioned theory supports Spiro, Feltovich, Jacobson, and Coulson’s Cognitive Flexibility Theory (1991). Their theory proposes that the nature of learning expands within a dynamic and unstructured environment. It emphasizes acquiring advanced information, enabling “a flexible rearrangement of existing knowledge to suit the requirements of a different situation” (Spiro, Feltovich, Jacobson Coulson, 1991). Essentially, this theory suggests that students enhance their ability to reconstruct knowledge as they respond to diverse circumstances (Spiro Jehng, 1990). Concerning this, the theory aligns with the study’s participants and teacher-researchers engaged in action research. They navigate challenges affecting their cognitive capacities and professional lives as they research. Moreover, this theory reinforces the effectiveness of the teachers’ coping strategies. Ultimately, this study is also underpinned by Albert Bandura’s Self-Efficacy Theory. Bandura defines self-efficacy as an individual’s belief and assurance in their ability to control their actions, motivation, achievements, and social surroundings (Bandura, 1995). This theory examines how a person’s self-perception and confidence in their capabilities influence the outcomes they achieve. Bandura and Adams (1977) further asserted that an individual’s self-efficacy could impact their choice of activities, the contexts in which they behave, and their persistence in the face of challenges and unfavorable experiences. Likewise, by applying Bandura’s Self-Efficacy Theory, we can uncover connections that elucidate how the study participants perceive themselves and their competencies within the context of the challenges they face, the strategies they employ to cope, and their insights into the execution of action research. This study relies on three key theories to understand how teacher-researchers tackle challenges in action research. First, Thorndike’s Trial and Error Theory (1938) suggests that learning happens through experimentation, mirroring how participants approach action research by trying different methods until they find practical solutions. Second, the Cognitive Flexibility Theory (Spiro et al., 1991) explains how individuals adapt their knowledge to various situations. In action research, teachers use flexible strategies to overcome obstacles and refine their approaches. Lastly, Bandura’s Self-Efficacy Theory (1995) explores how individuals’ confidence in their abilities influences their actions and persistence. In this study, understanding teachers’ self-belief sheds light on their choices and success in action research. By combining these theories, the study provides insights into how teacher-researchers navigate challenges and achieve their goals in action research. As presented in Figure 1, the theoretical

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

foundation underpins understanding the difficulties, strategies for managing them, and perceptions of teacher-researchers engaged in action research, which are constructed from various significant theoretical viewpoints, as out-

lined earlier. This framework offers a holistic insight into how these educator-researchers effectively navigate their professional responsibilities within the distinctive realm of conducting action research.

2. Methodology

This chapter delineates the systematic procedures and methodologies utilized in conducting phenomenological research, effectively addressing the study’s specific objectives. It also explicates the chosen research design and my roles during the study’s execution. Furthermore, it provides comprehensive insights into the research participants, elucidating their selection criteria and processes. Lastly, the chapter delves into the data collection methods, analysis, and strategies I have implemented to maintain ethical standards throughout the study.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study’s philosophical and qualitative presumptions are vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological. These assumptions established the groundwork for the research design I used in this study and informed my approach towards the study. A paradigm of a broad framework

or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided my choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall

research process and ensuring coherence in the study. **Ontology.** According to Grass (2024), ontology in research refers to the underlying beliefs about the nature of reality and what can be known about it. It addresses whether researchers view the empirical world as objective and independent of human perception (positivist stance) or as constructed and influenced by social and cultural contexts (constructivist). In this research study, the ontology guided my approach to gathering and interpreting data. For instance, I recognized that my participants have different experiences, realities, and understandings of a particular phenomenon—in this sense, their experiences as teachers and action researchers. Hence, the ontological principle guided me to use interviews and thematic analysis to capture the richness and complexity of their perspectives. **Epistemology.** According to Grass (2024), the concept of epistemology is applied in qualitative research by seeking objective knowledge. This means findings should be based on evidence, not influenced by personal biases, and can be tested and reproduced by others. This can be attained by using logical methods to assess evidence objectively. Simply put, I established this principle by noting that my research participants' views were separate from mine and that their responses could be validated and reproduced in future studies related to my research. Hence, I used Colaizzi's data analysis method to analyze the data drawn from my research participants objectively and ensured that I did not impose nor imply anything outside of the raw data of my research study. **Axiology.** In research, axiology refers to the study of values and how they influence the development and application of knowledge.

It examines the appropriateness, goodness, or badness of knowledge. It addresses ethical and aesthetic issues, determining what is considered valuable or important in human behavior and the environment (Rosida et al., 2023). I applied the concept of axiology by constantly revisiting the ethical considerations stipulated in this study, thereby sternly following them to make my study ethical and fair. **Methodology.** According to Grass (2024), methodology in research refers to the specific methods and strategies used to collect and analyze data to achieve scientific goals. It guides how a study was conducted through case studies, surveys, experiments, or other methods. Concerning my study, the methodology concept was applied when I specifically utilized a phenomenological research design that fits my study. Since I wanted to explore the teachers' experiences in conducting action research by finding patterns and themes that they corroborated, such a design was most suitable. Hence, the methodological concept was applied. **Rhetoric.** In research, rhetoric involves the adept and persuasive use of language, communication techniques, and presentation methods to convey ideas, arguments, and findings, ultimately influencing the audience's understanding and perspective on the study (Beqiri, 2018). In my study, I employed the narration of the research responses in an engaging and respectful narrative style to honor my research participants' voices while effectively highlighting the importance of the findings. This approach enhanced the readability of my research and ensured that the interpretations were robust and rooted in the participants' experiences.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Embracing a phenomenological research approach, my study aimed to delve into the experiences of teacher-researchers engaged in Action Research

within the Kiblawan South District public elementary schools. The goal was to extract insights into their coping mechanisms, experiences, and perspectives on the phenomenon

under investigation. Utilizing phenomenology as the guiding qualitative framework, my study sought to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the details of their experiences. As a researcher in this study, I advocated for a depth of inquiry that surpasses surface-level observations. The focus was to explore participants' perceptions, emotions, and reflections on the phenomenon. Recognizing the diverse perspectives shaped by my contexts, backgrounds, and per-

2.3. Design and Procedure—It was essential to define the specific approach set in a study to tailor the best research design, data collection, and data analysis approach according to its purpose. In this study, I utilized a qualitative research design. According to Hammerley (2023), qualitative research was suitable for studies that characterize verbal rather than statistical analysis. The qualitative design was the most appropriate given that I investigated lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of elementary teachers in conducting school-based research. This means that I, as a researcher, described and expounded on this phenomenon rather than proved or disproved hypotheses. However, specific approaches exist within qualitative research, such as grounded theory, narrative, case study, phenomenology, and ethnography. I employed a qualitative-phenomenological research design in this con-

2.4. Research Participants—A relatively smaller sample size in qualitative research is often sufficient compared to a quantitative study. The sample size in qualitative research should be adequate to capture feedback from a substantial number, if not all, of the viewpoints. Accommodating diverse perspectives reaches data saturation, a point at which adding more partici-

sonal histories, I underscored the importance of comprehending the complexities of the human experience (Neubauer et al., 2019). In line with this, the study emphasized in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives to capture the nature of teacher-researchers experiences. Adhering to phenomenological principles, my study aspired to contribute a rich understanding of the challenges, successes, coping strategies, and insights associated with being a teacher-researcher.

text that delves into the participants' lived experiences. I selected this method because the scientific aspect of phenomenological research centers on conveying the perspectives of the individuals under scrutiny and their significance to their experiences, followed by analyzing these perspectives using scientific concepts (Aspers, 2009). Moreover, Creswell (2019) defines phenomenological study as a research approach that details the shared and intricate experiences of individuals (participants) regarding a specific phenomenon. In phenomenology, a pivotal principle involves distilling one's interpretations of a given phenomenon into a universally applicable description. Accordingly, I aimed to uncover a phenomenon centered around the participants' journey in conducting action research. Subsequently, I gathered data from individuals with firsthand knowledge of this phenomenon, compiling comprehensive and precise descriptions.

pants does not yield new insights or data. Glaser and Strauss (1967) propose saturation to ascertain an appropriate sample size for qualitative research. As per Creswell (1998), a sample size of five (5) to 25 was advised for phenomenological studies, with Morse (1994) proposing a minimum of six (6). Nevertheless, no strict guidelines exist for selecting the right sample size

in qualitative research. Factors like time availability, resources, and study goals contribute to determining the most suitable sample size for a qualitative study (Patton, 1990). The study involved ten (10) teacher-researchers from various public elementary schools in the Kiblawan South District of Davao del Sur, with two from each school. These schools are Pasig Elementary School, Pocaleel Elementary School, Kisulan Elementary School, San Pedro Elementary School, and Emilio Jose Elementary School. There were two (2) representative teachers at each school. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in teaching service for at least three years; (2) must

be teachers who have undergone action research from the beginning up until the end; and (3) must be teaching in public elementary schools. I employed a purposive sampling design, selecting participants based on specific study criteria. Heath (2023) explained that purposive sampling was a qualitative research method that carefully chooses a particular group of individuals or elements for study. This selection was deliberate and not random, often called judgmental or selective sampling. In purposive sampling, the researcher has a defined objective when selecting the sample. As a result, the sample is chosen based on distinct characteristics or qualities the researcher intends to investigate.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations pertain to the moral principles and instructions that govern the conduct of research. They ensure that investigations are carried out responsibly, treating participants respectfully and striving to generate reliable and precise information. I adhered to the following ethical standards to protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community (Resnik, 2020). Social value concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. In this sense, I evaluated the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensured that resources were directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society. Informed consent. This describes obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after providing sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research, I ensured that participants fully understood the study and their rights, allowing them to make an informed decision about

whether to participate, thereby preserving their autonomy and dignity. Vulnerability of research pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors like age, cognitive ability, socioeconomic status, or health conditions. In this sense, I needed to acknowledge and consider prospective participants' potential vulnerability and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involved providing additional safeguards and support or modifying research methods to minimize possible adverse effects. Risks, benefits, and safety. In research, these elements are integral to evaluating the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study and implementing measures to safeguard the well-being of participants. In the realm of research, these aspects involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages associated with participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, I carefully assessed and balanced these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks and that adequate precautions are in place to minimize harm while optimizing the safety of participants. Privacy and confidentiality in research involve safeguarding

participants' personal information and ensuring their identities remain confidential unless they consent to the disclosure. In the context of this study, I was responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This included anonymizing data, securing figures by storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of both the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensured that her research was inclusive, avoiding the exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strived to make the research's benefits accessible to all who could benefit from it. This approach promoted fairness and equity throughout the research process. Transparency in research encompasses integrity in every research phase, from conception and execution to reporting results. I offered unambiguous and truthful information regarding her research, methodologies, and outcomes in this study. Furthermore, I was receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency serves as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and accountability both within the research community and among the general public. A researcher's qualification relates to one's academic background, professional background, and proficiency in a particular area of study, confirming that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to carry out the research capably. In this investigation, I held suitable qualifications that showcased my

capability to conduct research, analyze data, and make sense of the results. The adequacy of facilities in research addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. I guaranteed access to appropriate facilities for conducting my investigation in this research. This facilitated the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigated potential risks to study participants. Community involvement in research encompasses the dynamic participation and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engaged the community to guarantee the study's pertinence, acceptability, and potential influence. Additionally, this involvement fosters trust and cooperation between me and the community. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow academic honesty and integrity principles. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors. I maintained thorough documentation of my research procedures to guarantee that her work was devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries were authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I ensured that the research process was conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias or prejudice and influence from outside. I created an environment that encouraged the open and honest exploration of ideas and promoted fairness in data collection and analysis. As an expert

in qualitative methods, I was familiar with various qualitative research methods and techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. I have the skills and knowledge to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, assuring that the research question was satisfactorily addressed and that the results were legitimate and dependable. As a data collector

and keeper, I gathered information from various sources, such as interviews or observations, and ensured accurate and secure information storage. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured that data was structured and available for later examination and understanding. As a data analyst, I analyzed the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives per the research query. I utilized meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowl-

edge base within my discipline. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I was tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entailed skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I guaranteed that the research results were easily reachable and understandable to the designated audience.

2.7. Data Collection—The research aimed to investigate the challenges faced by teacher researchers in conducting action research. I described data collection procedures to attain the utmost transparency and clarity in the research study. Detailed descriptions of the process are provided as follows: Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. I began the data collection process by securing an endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School at Rizal Memorial College. This involved submitting a formal letter outlining the research objectives and methodology, along with any supporting documents. This undertaking was scheduled within the last two weeks of August 2023. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon receiving the endorsement, I asked permission from the school's division superintendent. This required a similar formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Also, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 with the research instrument, explaining the study's objectives and the participants' identification. Moreover, I waited for the response of the SDS before conducting it. This was done for the first two weeks of September 2023. Asking for permission from the school heads. Once the permission was granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institu-

tions. This step involved submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked permission from the third week of September 2023 to the last week of the said month. Obtaining consent from the participants. With the school heads' approval, I obtained consent from the research participants. This was done through informed consent forms explaining the research purpose, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. Consent from the participants was obtained in October 2023. Conducting the interview. Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interview took place in the first two weeks of October 2023. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribed the interviewees' remarks, carefully considering non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure uses audio recordings and field notes to comprehensively capture the breadth of participants' reactions. The transcription of interviewee responses was scheduled for the third week of October 2023. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. Lastly, I embarked on data coding and thematic content analysis.

This involved methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. Discerning patterns and connections within the data,

2.8. Data Analysis—After collecting the data, I began data coding and thematic content analysis. This involved methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and gleaned insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allowed me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of the participants. I employed Colaizzi's method of data analysis in this study. Since the study covers different perspectives and portrayals of participants' responses concerning action research, such a method effectively explores the research participants' responses clearly and logically. According to Wirihana (2018), Colaizzi's approach to data analysis is rigorous and robust,

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The analytical framework in phenomenological research is a systematic and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I used Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their experiences in extra-curricular activities. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process offering rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can

I formulated conclusions and gleaned insights into the research objectives. This task was done in the third and last weeks of October 2023.

making it a qualitative method that guarantees the trustworthiness and dependability of its outcomes. It enables researchers to uncover emerging themes and their intricate relationships. The methodology involved multiple readings of each transcript to grasp its content comprehensively. Significant statements about the phenomenon were identified and extracted from each transcript, meticulously documented on separate sheets with corresponding page and line references. Meanings were derived from these statements and categorized into groups, clusters of themes, and overarching themes. The study's findings were synthesized into a detailed depiction of the phenomenon, elucidating its essential structure. Finally, validation was sought from the research participants to confirm that the descriptive findings accurately mirrored their experiences.

be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore their intricate relationships (Wirihana et al., 2018). Data Familiarization. By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aim to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process is crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. Identifying Significant Statements. I carefully identify every statement in the narratives directly related to the phenomenon I

am studying. To identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step is essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a solid basis for future thematic development.

Formulating Meanings. After carefully examining the critical statements, I determine meanings pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Colaizzi admits that complete bracketing is impossible, I must reflexively "bracket" my presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants' experiences, this process entails putting aside my interpretations as much as is practical.

Clustering Themes. I ensure a rigorous analysis that remains true to the participants' experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. Allowing the themes to naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces preserves the integrity of the analysis.

Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporate

every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon I write. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it is ensured that the final representation presents a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant has had.

Producing the fundamental structure. I break down the lengthy explanation into a brief, concise statement highlighting the key elements that I believe are crucial to understanding the phenomenon's structure. This succinct synthesis effectively and concisely communicates the essence of the participants' experiences, concentrating on the essential components necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I ask participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience by returning it to all participants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I may change the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings are increased, and the analysis is firmly based on the participants' perspectives.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study refers to how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results are, ensuring that the conclusions are trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate the study's reliability. According to Guba (1981), these considerations were further described below.

Credibility. Credibility refers to how much trust one has in research findings being factual. It confirms if the findings are based on the data collected from interviews and if the interpretation and reporting of the data accu-

rately represent their actual meaning. To establish credibility, I used methods such as member checking (presenting findings to participants for their feedback), prolonged engagement (spending sufficient time with participants), and triangulation (using multiple data sources or methods to confirm findings). This helped ensure that my interpretations were faithful to the participants' viewpoints.

Transferability. This refers to the degree to which the research findings of a particular qualitative inquiry could be transferred to other settings and could be applied by other respondents. I enhanced transferability by providing detailed descriptions of the research

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

methods, context, and participants, which allows readers to assess the applicability of findings to their situations. Providing thick descriptions and context-rich narratives helped readers determine whether the findings could be relevant in their contexts. **Confirmability.** This establishes whether the research data and interpretations of the findings were figments of the investigator's imagination or entirely derived from the respondents' statements. The research established confirmability by maintaining an audit trail and documenting the research process, decisions, and changes made along the way. This transparency could allow researchers to follow my thought process and decisions, enhancing the credibility of the findings. Additionally, techniques such as peer debriefing with

other researchers or with the help of my adviser helped minimize personal biases. **Dependability.** This pertains to the extent to which the research findings are stable over time. Dependability establishes whether the research findings would be consistently repeated if the research were to be replicated, either with the same investigator or with another, either in the same context or in a different one. I achieved dependability by clearly documenting the research process, including data collection methods, data analysis procedures, and any changes during the study. By following a systematic and well-documented approach, other researchers could replicate my study and achieve similar results, enhancing the findings' dependability.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and the responses of teacher-researchers in action research on the said questions. These participants shared their experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights in conducting Action Research within the scope of Kiblawan South District public elementary schools. This study intended to gain insights from the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of teacher-researchers regarding the phenomenon being investigated.

3.1. The experiences of teacher-researchers In conducting Action Research — Teacher researchers engaged in action research often confront challenges during their investigative journeys. These dedicated educators

balance the demands of their classrooms and navigate the complexities of research design, data collection, and analysis; hence, they have their fair share of facing various challenges in conducting their action research.

3.1.1. Time constraints—Teacher-researchers often grapple with significant time constraints when engaged in action research. Balancing the demands of classroom instruction with the rigorous data collection and analysis process can be a formidable challenge, requiring careful planning and prioritization of tasks to ensure the research process remains feasible within the constraints of the academic calendar. Based on the collected responses, it is evident that educators engaged in research endeavors encounter considerable challenges in executing

their action research projects, with time constraints emerging as the foremost impediment to their successful completion. Teachers are often tasked with the dual responsibilities of pedagogy and administrative duties, thereby rendering action research an additional and demanding commitment. Moreover, the temporal constraints are further exacerbated by various extrinsic and intrinsic factors, including but not limited to personal circumstances, dispositions, and behavioral patterns, all of which play a pivotal role in shaping the feasibility of under-

taking action research initiatives. In line with this, according to Enero (2020), lack of time is one of the challenges lecturers can face in conducting action research. Such a challenge limits the depth and scope of the entire action research process, potentially compromising the study's overall effectiveness and outcomes. The teacher-researchers responses above, which generated

3.1.2. Research Skills Deficiency—Meanwhile, educators venturing into action research often need help with a significant challenge: a lack of proficiency in research abilities. This lack of proficiency can present a considerable obstacle, impeding their capacity to methodically collect, rigorously analyze, and meaningfully interpret data. As a result, educators may find themselves in a constant quest for additional guidance and resources to bridge this knowledge gap and enhance the quality and impact of their research initiatives. Derived from the responses provided by the participants, it is indisputable that a dearth of proficiency in action research skills influences the successful execution of their studies. Certain participants found it imperative to revisit prior discussions, while others resorted to online tutorials to facilitate their challenges. Nevertheless, it underscores the pervasive issue of teacher researchers grappling with unfamiliarity, inadequacy, and an absence of theoretical guidance that obstructs their research endeavors. Accordingly, Khankeh et al. (2015) have argued that a lack of knowledge, experience, and research skills can impede the transmission of information or the en-

3.1.3. Heavy Workloads—Teacher-researchers also need help with the daunting challenge of conducting action research due to their heavy workloads, encompassing administrative responsibilities and teaching demands. Balancing the intricacies of classroom instruction, grading, and administrative duties can leave teachers feeling stretched thin, making

this theme, are also solidified by Berenguel and Villamor's study (2023), wherein they interviewed 30 teachers in JBT Caing Sr. Memorial Integrated School, Sarangani Province. These teachers encountered significant challenges in conducting action research, which included time constraints.

hancement of existing knowledge when trying to comprehend a phenomenon under study. Norasmah and Chia (2016) further emphasized that a profound understanding of action research practices may hinder teachers from implementing this methodology due to their lack of comprehension and necessary skills. This lack of clarity and proficiency among teachers is supported by the findings of Gomez and Catan (2021), who investigated teachers' experiences in action research within the Department of Education (DepEd)-Leyte Division. Their study revealed that public school teachers engaging in research often faced issues related to inadequate research proficiency. Similarly, Nurhasanah et al. (2020) identified similar challenges in Indonesia. Teachers from various provinces in Indonesia reported struggling with several aspects of classroom action research, including a deficiency in theoretical understanding, limited proficiency in formulating data collection instruments, insufficient skills in data analysis, inadequate abilities in composing research reports, and difficulty navigating the complex regulations governing the dissemination of their research findings.

it difficult to allocate the necessary time and mental energy required for action research. The weight of these combined responsibilities can sometimes be a barrier to pursuing meaningful inquiry. The research participants highlighted that while they acknowledged the value of engaging in action research and perceived it as a potentially straightforward endeavor, the de-

mands of administrative and teaching duties and the expectations imposed by the department and school made it a formidable struggle. Consequently, carrying out action research evolved into a complex and demanding endeavor that stretched their time management and energy. In line with this idea, Han (2017) and Negi (2018) endorse the notion that the effectiveness of teacher researchers in conducting action research may be compromised due to their excessively large class sizes and demanding workloads, which leave them with insufficient time to engage in research activities. In con-

3.1.4. Lack of Financial Backing—Teacher-researchers also encounter financial constraints as a significant challenge in conducting action research. This predicament arises because it requires resources for various essential components, such as conducting surveys or assessments, honorariums for the participants, investing in teaching tools, and professional development workshops. These financial limitations hinder them from implementing their research projects effectively. Among other challenges the research participants have faced is the need for more funding or financial constraints. Budget is crucial in action research as it directly impacts the scope and feasibility of the action research project. Sufficient funding ensures access to necessary resources, training, and sup-

3.1.5. Participants' Apathy—Teachers also encounter challenges when their participants exude a sense of apathy in their study. This attitude can make the research process feel like an uphill battle as educators strive to engage and inspire those they seek to involve. It prompts deep reflection on the importance of their work and a continuous effort to find innovative ways to spark enthusiasm and genuine interest among their participants.

formity with these is the study conducted by Tingabngab and Binayao (2023) exploring the challenges faced by the sixteen public-school teachers of Talisayan District, Division of Misamis Oriental, in conducting action research during the school year 2020-2021. The findings revealed that their priorities in teaching affected their action research conduct. More so, Tindowen et al., in their study in 2019, have found that increased workload and teacher responsibilities affect teachers' competence in conducting action research.

port, enabling teacher researchers to implement effective interventions and gather meaningful data for informed decision-making. To substantiate the teacher-researchers' responses, Ulla (2018) contended that the lack of school financial support for researchers could prevent the latter from completing the undertaking. Likewise, Gomez and Catan's study (2021) in the Department of Education – Leyte Division also unveiled the constrained financial backing as a hindrance to teachers engaged in research. Furthermore, Abrenica and Cascolan (2022) corroborated the study by looking at the experiences of 50 teachers conducting action research in Pangasinan Division II high schools. According to the participants, financial restrictions are also one of the problems they have encountered in doing action research.

In line with the responses, it can be understood that the presence of apathy or demotivation among participants led teacher-researchers to question the impact and relevance of their research. It raises concerns about whether their study adequately addresses the needs and concerns of those they aim to serve. Teacher-researchers often find themselves adapting their approaches, seeking fresh perspectives, and refining their methods to overcome these chal-

lenges and ensure that their research makes a meaningful contribution to the field of education and the participants' lives. At times, participants may hesitate to participate fully in data collection, requiring researchers to exert extra effort to ensure their involvement. Sarkar (2014), as referenced by Bullo et al. (2021), highlights a critical problem faced by teacher-researchers engaged in action research: the acquisition of permission and the recruitment of participants for their studies. This challenge is further exacerbated by the need to follow institutional protocols, establish trust with potential participants, and ensure ethical considerations are met throughout the research process. Tingabngab and Binayao (2023) certified this as they explored the challenges faced by the public-school teachers of Talisayan District, Division of Misamis Oriental, in conducting action research during the school year 2020-2021. The findings revealed that teacher-researchers experienced being rejected by their research partici-

pants during their action research data collection process. Figure 3 encapsulates the challenges faced by teacher researchers in action research. Firstly, teacher-researchers need more action research skills, hampering the quality and rigor of their investigations, as cited by T1, T2, T4, T6, and T7. Secondly, it also proves that action research is challenging due to participants' apathy, which undermines the effectiveness of the study according to T1, T2, T5, T7, and T9. Moreover, the lack of financial backing restricts resources for data collection, analysis tools, and participant incentives, further complicating research endeavors, as also mentioned by T2, T3, T4, T6, and T7. Lastly, time constraints emerge as a challenge as teacher-researchers struggle to balance their teaching responsibilities, administrative duties, and personal commitments with the demands of research. Following the responses of T3, T5, T7, T8, and T10, this often results in rushed or incomplete projects.

3.2. *The coping mechanisms of teacher-researchers In conducting Action Research* — Teacher-researchers have encountered a multifaceted spectrum of challenges throughout the various stages of the action research process, encompassing the pre-, intra-, and post-

research phases. They have deployed various coping strategies and mechanisms in response to these demands, exemplifying their resilience and adaptability. In doing so, teacher-researchers have demonstrated their best capacity to hit their research trajectories.

3.2.1. *Seeking Support Networks*—In action research, teachers recognize the invaluable role of support networks in fortifying their scholarly pursuits. These networks encompass colleagues, mentors, and fellow educators who provide guidance, encouragement, and a sounding board for ideas. This collaborative ethos forms a cornerstone of their approach, enabling them to tackle challenges collectively and fostering a sense of camaraderie on their research journey. From the responses, it can be inferred that teacher-researchers in action researchers

seek support from their fellow educators and co-researchers, mentors and colleagues, or any available online community concerning action research. Accordingly, considering research support may enhance teachers' engagement in research activities. Existing evidence suggests the importance of comprehensive support systems, resources, and collaborative efforts to overcome obstacles and encourage teachers to engage in action research, enhancing their professional development and improving the education system (Codilla Yangson-Barot, 2023).

Fig. 3. The Experiences of Teacher-Researchers in Conducting Action Research

Furthermore, a study backs up the act of teacher-researchers seeking support from school—that be, in turn, of teachers, mentorships, or colleagues. A survey conducted by Gonzales et al. (2020) with public elementary teachers in the Schools Division of Nueva Vizcaya revealed that despite the problems of action research that teachers have faced, they were more capable of doing and finishing it because of the research support and opportunities they received from the

3.2.2. Balancing Administrative Workloads—Amidst the rigorous demands of teaching and the added commitment of action research, educators face the intricate task of harmonizing their administrative workloads. Achieving this equilibrium is essential for maintaining their research momentum and the quality of their teaching. Striking this balance requires meticulous planning and efficient time management, ensuring their educational and research responsibilities coexist harmoniously. From the responses, it can be gleaned that teacher-researchers in action research find time to balance their action research conduct with their administrative responsibilities, creating systems and processes to make ends meet. In line with this, Aguilar-De Borja's (2018) study, referenced by Abrenica and Cascolan (2022), highlights a pertinent coping mechanism. De-

3.2.3. Professional Development—Pursuing professional development is a paramount strategy for teachers engaged in action research. They actively seek opportunities to enhance their pedagogical skills and research understanding through workshops, seminars, and conferences. These endeavors enrich their knowledge base and empower them with the latest research methodologies and educational insights, ultimately elevating their effectiveness in the classroom. From the responses, it can be de-

school and the technical assistance they received from their supervisors or experienced teachers they were assigned. This aligns with the findings of Tarrayo et al. (2021), who proposed that maintaining motivation and commitment to research involvement can pose difficulties and challenges. However, sustaining enthusiasm and engagement in research activities remains possible under conducive conditions and a supportive research environment.

spite the challenge of teachers facing time constraints, the research emphasizes the importance of proactively balancing and managing time as a coping strategy. It suggests that educators must prioritize allocating time for their research endeavors, underlining the significance of effective time management practices. More so, this has been solidified by Tulung et al. (2022), who stated in their research that inadequate time management poses a barrier for teachers when implementing Classroom Action Research (CAR). Therefore, teachers should organize their work schedules to prevent conflicts. Establishing a suitable program for task execution in alignment with planned schedules enhances teacher dedication. Their study also suggested that teachers cultivate effective self-management skills, mainly through proficient time management.

duced that teacher-researchers actively pursue professional development opportunities to expand their knowledge of action research. This includes participating in workshops, seminars, training, and conferences in this study area. In line with this, Tarrayo et al. (2020) investigated teacher researchers and their research practices from the perspective of English language educators in the Philippines. The study unveiled notable, unique coping strategies and mechanisms educators employ in doing their research.

This includes active involvement in research-centered dialogues with peers within the department, continuous research-related reading in language education, participation in updated academic conferences, and pursuit of postgraduate research engagements. Other studies also

3.2.4. Professional and Educational Motivations—The motivation to conduct action research extends beyond pursuing academic milestones or professional progression; it embodies a profound commitment to continuous improvement. Teachers embarking on this path are driven by the desire to elevate their teaching practices, contribute to the educational field, and effect positive change in their classrooms. Their dedication to their academic journey and career aspirations propels them forward with unwavering enthusiasm. From the responses, it can be inferred that teacher-researchers also conduct action research due to their professional and educational motivations. Teachers want to improve their teaching practices while advancing their careers in the field. By this, Ulla (2018) found that the prospect of career advancement or further academic degrees drives teacher-researchers. His study in Agusan del Norte revealed that many teachers were motivated by pursuing higher education, particularly master's and Ph.D. degrees. These educators focused on meeting their degree requirements and aligning their research efforts with educational milestones. Additionally, job promotion emerged as a significant motivation, with many

3.3. The educational insights of teacher-researchers in conducting Action Research—Teacher-researchers engaged in the dynamic realm of action research have acquired invaluable educational insights throughout their journey. They recognize the manifold benefits

found that workshops, training, and seminars related to research are essential for teacher-researchers. This dramatically impacts the action research journey and professional development of teacher-researchers (Nagibova, 2019).

viewing research as a pathway to career advancement and salary increases. This relates to the findings of Salcedo and Relucio (2019), who discovered that SHS instructors exhibit low confidence in utilizing action research for professional growth. However, despite this, they hold a positive view of the impact of research, recognizing its potential to enhance their research capabilities and contribute to improvements in teaching and interpersonal interactions with students. Moreover, Ulla et al. (2017), as cited by Codilla Yangson-Barot (2023), illustrated that teacher participants held a positive attitude toward research and its advantages for their teaching practice and students' learning. Consequently, the motivation for teacher research is primarily fueled by the prospect of job promotion. Figure 4 illustrates the pragmatic approaches adopted by teacher researchers to steer the challenges inherent in conducting action research. Firstly, they actively seek support networks, recognizing the value of collaboration and shared experiences in overcoming obstacles, as cited by T3, T4, T6, and T8. Secondly, they prioritize balancing their administrative duties alongside research commitments, ensuring neither aspect compromises the other according to T2, T5, T8, and T9.

of action research, acknowledging its power to transform teaching and learning practices. However, they have also experienced the inherent challenges in this process, recognizing that pursuing meaningful change is challenging. Moreover, these dedicated educators have

Fig. 4. The Coping Mechanisms of Teacher-Researchers in Conducting Action Research

honed significant values and skills, underscoring the profound personal and professional growth that can be derived from this transformative approach to inquiry and practice.

3.3.1. Action Research is beneficial— Through rigorous engagement in action research, teachers have come to a profound realization - that inquiry and self-reflection enhance their teaching practices. They have witnessed firsthand the tangible benefits that action research can bring to the classroom, from tailored instructional strategies to heightened student engagement. This insight has strengthened their resolve to continue harnessing the power of action research as a powerful tool for educational improvement. From the research participants' responses, it can be inferred that they consider action research a transformative experience as they believe that this undertaking benefits them as educators, the learning environment, and the students themselves. In line with the statements and claims, Abrenica and Cascolan (2022) solidify this as their research study with several 50 teacher participants in Pangasinan Division II high schools revealed that action research positively impacts teaching-learning in one's professional development and curriculum creation or development. Additionally, according to Lufungulo et al. (2021), action research holds significance in education as it promotes reflective teaching and learning, broadens teachers' pedagogical skill sets, enhances instructional quality, strengthens the link between practice and student outcomes, cultivates receptiveness to innovation, and empowers educators to take ownership of the knowledge they generate.

3.3.2. Action Research is a Challenging Process— For teachers who have embarked on the path of action research, the journey has been a revelation of its own. They have learned that the research process is complex and demanding, requiring meticulous planning, dedication, and resilience. The challenges they have faced, whether in designing robust research methodologies or navigating data analysis, have illuminated the rigorous nature of this pursuit. Yet, in acknowledging these challenges, they have embraced them as opportunities for growth, recognizing that the transformative power of action research often lies in its inherent complexity. As described by the participants, action research is a multifaceted and detail-oriented endeavor requiring careful navigation through numerous processes. They emphasized its rigorous and uncertain nature yet acknowledged its undeniable role in fostering personal and professional growth. In the same breath and context, Negi (2018) surveyed the problems of secondary-level teachers in an EFL context, with a sample of 46 teachers teaching purposely selected from 46 different schools in the Baitadi district in the Far Western part of Nepal. Later on, the study indicated that 70.45 of the teacher-researchers population did not know that it is one of the practical tools for reflective practice, and (63.63) of the teachers needed to be more familiar with the action research processes. This means they know the definition of action research but need help. Oestar and Marzo (2022) found similar results, indicating that teacher researchers need help selecting data analysis tools, encoding quantitative and qualitative data, and interpreting software-generated results. Moreover, Rochsantiningasih (2022) highlights that despite the challenges associated with conducting action research, teachers experienced numerous benefits from engaging in it.

3.3.3. Learned Significant Skills and Values —

One of the most profound insights gained from conducting action research is acquiring significant values and skills extending far beyond the research's confines. Teachers have discovered the importance of patience, persistence, and adaptability in facing obstacles. They have honed their skills in data analysis, critical thinking, and reflective practice, all of which have enriched their teaching toolkit. Moreover, they have developed a deep appreciation for collaboration, open-mindedness, and lifelong learning, realizing that these qualities are integral to research success and their continued growth as educators. Per the participants' reflections, they recognized substantial value and acquired essential skills throughout the action research process. They cultivated patience, persistence, open-mindedness, and adaptability. Moreover, they asserted that their critical thinking and collaborative abilities were notably strengthened. Accordingly, Albalawi and Johnson (2022) solidify this claim by conducting a study to determine the degree of public school teachers' skills regarding action research. The study sample included public school teachers from the Kalamazoo metropolitan area, United States, and Tabuk, Saudi Arabia. The study revealed that teachers believed that action research enhanced their research skills in identifying a problem, developing a research plan, and investigating or validating the outcomes of an action research study. More so, their responses ranged from confidence in handling and interpreting data, being better equipped to find practical solutions to teaching and learning, assisting English as a second language (ESL) and special education teachers in understanding the history of students, preparing profiles of ESL and exceptional education pupils, and enhanced ability for self-gauging metrics. Additionally, Tindowen et al. (2019) discovered that action research could enhance teaching and learning methods, maximize pedagogical understanding, and foster favorable impacts on student learning. Aguilarde Borja (2018), as cited by Codilla Yangson-Barot (2023), found that almost all teachers observed favorable effects on student learning and their teaching methods through their action research initiatives. These studies collectively highlight the significant contribution of action research in improving the teaching and learning dynamics, as perceived and assessed by educators. Figure 5 encapsulates the distilled insights of teacher-researchers engaged in action research, highlighting three fundamental observations. Firstly, they universally recognize the inherent benefits of action research, viewing it as a valuable tool for professional and personal growth, as mentioned by T1, T3, T4, T7, and T8. Secondly, they candidly acknowledge the challenges embedded within the action research process, understanding its complexity and demanding nature, as cited by T2, T3, T4, T5, and T9. Lastly, they emphasized acquiring invaluable values and skills through their engagement with action research, underscoring its transformative potential in fostering patience, resilience, critical thinking, and collaboration among practitioners. (T1, T2, T4, T6, and T10).

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, I present a summary of the study. I derived implications and future directions from the findings summarized here. My research aimed to investigate the experiences, coping strategies, and insights of teacher-researchers who conducted action research in various public elementary schools within the Kiblawan South District of Davao del Sur. To achieve my research objectives, I employed a qualitative phenomenological research design and utilized thematic analysis for data analysis, following the approach outlined by Creswell (2019). In this study, I

Fig. 5. The Educational Insights of Teacher-Researchers in Conducting Action Research.

comprehensively describe the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights shared by elementary school teachers who have conducted action research. These teachers possess valuable knowledge about the phenomenon under investigation, which was thoroughly discussed in the previous chapter.

4.1. Findings—Based on the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, several findings and themes were revealed. Firstly, a prevalent deficiency in research skills emerges as a hurdle, indicating a need for further training and support in this domain. Moreover, the lack of financial backing poses a notable constraint, inhibiting teachers' ability to execute research projects effectively. Time constraints also feature prominently, underscoring the struggle to balance teaching responsibilities with research commitments. Furthermore, the apathy displayed by research participants adds another layer of complexity, potentially dampening enthusiasm and impeding the research process. In exploring how teacher researchers cope with the challenges inherent in conducting action research, the study unveils effective mechanisms educators employ to navigate these obstacles. Notably, seeking support networks emerges as a pivotal strategy, enabling teachers to exchange ideas, troubleshoot problems, and garner emotional encouragement

4.2. Implications—The first main research question, which discussed teacher-researchers experiences conducting action research, unveiled that many lacked research skills and experienced participants' apathy during their study. This identified challenge among teacher researchers underscores the need for ongoing professional development programs tailored to them. Schools, school districts, and educational institutions like DepEd or CHED may invest in training opportunities that empower educators with research skills, methodologies, and techniques. Tailored workshops and courses should be designed to bridge the gap between

from peers and mentors. Professional development initiatives also play a crucial role, empowering educators with the necessary skills and knowledge to surmount research-related hurdles effectively. Moreover, balancing administrative, professional, and educational workloads proves instrumental in ensuring teachers can allocate sufficient time and energy to their research endeavors without compromising other responsibilities. Ultimately, this research study gave insights from teacher-researchers conducting action research within educational settings. The results illuminate the challenging nature of action research, highlighting the complexities involved in the process. Despite its challenges, the study also emphasizes the benefits of action research within the educational field. Moreover, it sheds light on the significant values and skills that teacher-researchers developed through their engagement in action research, emphasizing the enhanced capabilities and expertise they gain as practitioners within their professional communities.

pedagogical expertise and research proficiency. Meanwhile, participants mentioned that they also experienced the effects of the lack of financial backing for their action research studies, allowing them to use personal funds to sustain and complete their studies. This highlights the importance of allocating sufficient resources to support teacher-research initiatives. Educational policymakers should consider budgetary allocations for action research projects providing funds for materials, equipment, and stipends for participating teachers. Granting opportunities and funding mechanisms should also be expanded to encourage more teachers to engage

in meaningful research. Furthermore, teacher researchers experience the impact of time constraints during their respective studies due to tight deadlines and heavy workloads. As there may be times that they could not control the circumstances during their conduct, it would be essential to instill work-life balance. With this, educational leaders may explore flexible scheduling options to accommodate research activities within teachers' daily responsibilities. They can establish dedicated time slots or "research days" to facilitate teachers' engagement in action research without compromising their instructional duties. With these conclusions and their implications, public elementary schools from Kiblawan South, Davao Del Sur, can further improve the situation of teacher researchers conducting action research.

4.3. Future Directions—While this phenomenological study has shed light on the lived experiences of teacher-researchers conducting action research in Kiblawan South District, Davao City, it also reveals several promising avenues for future research endeavors. These future directions can deepen our understanding of the challenges, coping mechanisms, and implications of action research in elementary school settings: Longitudinal studies may benefit future research due to the nature of teaching and the evolving education landscape. Tracking teacher-researchers experiences over an extended period would provide insights into how their challenges and coping mechanisms evolve and how these experiences impact their professional growth and practice through longitudinal studies. Another is through Comparative Analysis. Comparative research may explore variations in teacher-researcher experiences across different schools, districts, or regions. This approach could identify contextual factors contributing to the challenges faced and the effectiveness of coping mechanisms. On the other hand, intervention studies may also be built upon the coping mechanisms identified in this study so that future research could focus on developing and implementing targeted interventions to address teacher researchers' challenges. These interventions could include professional development programs, mentoring initiatives, or resource allocation strategies to mitigate research skills deficiencies, financial constraints, and heavy workloads. Ultimately, since this study's research design is phenomenological with ten participants, expanding the scope of the study to include a more diverse population of teacher-researchers, such as those from different grade levels, subject areas, or cultural backgrounds, could provide a richer understanding of the challenges and coping mechanisms in action research. In conclusion, this phenomenological study has laid a foundation for further exploration of the lived experiences of teacher-researchers conducting action research in elementary school settings. These future research directions can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities associated with action research, ultimately benefiting educators and students in improving educational practices and outcomes.

5. References

- Abelardo, L. J., Lomboy, M. A. A., Lopez, C. C., Balaria, F. E., & Subia, G. S. (2019). Challenges encountered by the national high school teachers in doing action research. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences (IJELS)*, 4(4). <http://journalrepository.co/index.php/ijels/article/view/7>

- Abrenica, J. T., & Cascolan, H. M. S. (2022). Impact of action research in education: Experiences and challenges faced by teachers. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*, 5(2), 1–15.
- Aguilar-de Borja, J. M. (2018). Teacher action research: Its difficulties and implications. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 6(1), 29–35.
- Albalawi, A., & Johnson, L. N. (2022). Action research skills among public school teachers: A cross-cultural study. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 8(2), 286–310.
- Antonio Jr, T. E. (2020). Master teachers' challenges in doing action research: A case study. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(7), 2990–2995.
- Aspers, P. (2009). Empirical phenomenology: A qualitative research approach (the cologne seminars). *Indo-Pacific Journal of Phenomenology*, 9(2), 1–12.
- Bandura, A. (1995). *Self-efficacy in changing societies*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bandura, A., & Adams, N. E. (1977). Analysis of the self-efficacy theory of behavioral change. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 1(4), 287–310.
- Behforouz, B., Al Ghaithi, A., & Al Weshahi, S. (2023). Lecturers' perceptions of action research and current challenges. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 22(3), 141–159.
- Berenguel, D., & Villamor, E. (2023). Assessing the teachers' experiences in action research based on swot analysis. *West African Journal of Educational Sciences and Practice*, 2(1), 33–39.
- Boeskens, L., Nusche, D., & Yurita, M. (2020). *Policies to support teachers' continuing professional learning: A conceptual framework and mapping of oecd data* (tech. rep.).
- Bourner, T., & Brook, C. (2019). Comparing and contrasting action research and action learning. In *The wiley handbook of action research in education* (pp. 185–205).
- Bullo, M. M., Labastida, R. T., & Manlapas, C. C. (2021). Challenges and difficulties encountered by teachers in the conduct of educational research: Basis for teachers' enhancement program. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 10(13), 67–75.
- Caulfield, J. (2020). *How to do thematic analysis* [Retrieved August 28, 2023]. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/thematic-analysis/>
- Chilisa, B., & Kawulich, B. (n.d.). Selecting a research approach: Paradigm, methodology, and methods [n.d.]. https://yuli-elearning.com/pluginfile.php/4360/mod_resource/content/1/Paradigma%20Penelitian.pdf
- Cognitive flexibility theory* [Retrieved August 28, 2023]. (n.d.). <http://www.personal.psu.edu/wxh139/CFT.htm>
- Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W. (2019). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (2nd). Sage Publications.
- Crotty, M. J. (1998). *The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process*. The foundations of social research.
- Dawadi, S. (2021). Thematic analysis approach: A step-by-step guide for elt research practitioners. *Journal of NELTA*, 25(1-2), 62–71.

- Do 16, s. 2017. research management guidelines [Retrieved August 06, 2023]. (n.d.). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2017/03/20/do-16-s-2017-researchmanagement-guidelines/>
- George, T. (2023). *What is action research?: Definition & examples* [Retrieved June 22, 2023]. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/action-research/>
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Aldine.
- Gomez, M. A., & Catan, M. M. (2021). Factors leading to limited research conducted by philippine public school teachers. *Innovare Journal of Education*, 9(3), 1–7.
- Gonzales, I. B., Corpuz, D. A., & Dellosa, R. M. (2020). Research capabilities of public elementary school teachers and management support of the schools division of nueva vizcaya, philippines. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 8(4).
- Guba, E. G. (1981). Criteria for assessing the trustworthiness of naturalistic inquiries. *Educational Communication and Technology Journal*, 29(2), 75–91. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF0276677>
- Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1989). *Fourth-generation evaluation*. Sage.
- Hammersley, M. (2023). *Defining qualitative research*. Bloomsbury Collections. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5040/9781849666084.ch-001>
- Han, L. (2017). Analysis of the problems in language teachers’ action research. *International Education Studies*, 10(11), 123–128.
- Heath, C. (2023). *What is purposive sampling? technique, examples, and faqs* [Retrieved February 5, 2023]. <https://dovetail.com/research/purposive-sampling/#:~:text=Purpose%20sampling%20is%20a%20technique,judgmental%20sampling%20or%20selective%20sampling>
- Hine, G. S. (2013). The importance of action research in teacher education programs. *Issues in Educational Research*, 23(2), 151–163.
- Jr, L. L. C., & Yangson-Barot, H. (2023). Teachers as researchers: An emphasis on the readiness and attitude towards action research. *International Journal*, 10(3), 657–671.
- Kemmis, S., & McTaggart, R. (1988). *The action research planner*. Deakin University Press.
- Khankeh, e. a. (2015). Challenges in conducting qualitative research in health: A conceptual paper. *Iranian Journal of Nursing and Midwifery Research*.
- Lufungulo, E. S., Mambwe, R., & Kalinde, B. (2021). The meaning and role of action research in education. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Language and Social Sciences Education*, 4(2), 115–128.
- McLaughlin, C., & Ayubayeva, N. (2015). ‘it is the research of self-experience’: Feeling the value in action research. *Educational Action Research*, 23(1), 51–67.
- Morse, J. M. (1994). Designing funded qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research* (2nd). Sage.
- Nagibova, G. (2019). Professional development: The challenges of action research implementation in kazakhstan. *International Academy Journal Web of Scholar*, 2(9 (39)), 17–24.
- Oestar, J., & Marzo, C. (2022). Teachers as researchers: Skills and challenges in action research making. *International Journal of Theory and Application in Elementary and Secondary School Education*, 4(2), 95–104.
- Resnik, D. B. (2020). What is ethics in research, & why is it important? [Retrieved August 18, 2023, from <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/resources/bioethics/whatis/index.cfm>].

- Rochsantiningsih, D. (2022). *Enhancing professional development of Indonesian high school teachers through action research* [Doctoral dissertation]. Macquarie University.
- Salcedo-Relucio, M. A. (2019). The dilemma in conducting an action research as a tool for professional development of the senior high school teachers. *Southeast Asian Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(1), 12–24.
- Salmons, J. E. (2019). *Find the theory in your research*. Little Quick Fix.
- Sandberg, J., & Alvesson, M. (2020). Meanings of theory: Clarifying theory through typification. *Journal of Management Studies*, 58(2), 487–516.
- Sarkar, M. (2014). Challenges in conducting educational research: The case of a developing country. In *Contemporary approaches to research in mathematics, science, health, and environmental education*.
- Shaik-Abdullah, S., Shanmugam, S. K. S., & Chinnappan, M. (2020). Action research as continuous professional development in southeast Asia. In *Oxford research encyclopedia of education*.
- Tarrayo, V. N., Hernandez, P. J. S., & Claustro, J. M. A. S. (2020). Teachers and research practices: Perspectives from English language educators in a Philippine university. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education (Online)*, 45(12), 73–90.
- Tarrayo, V. N., Hernandez, P. J. S., & Claustro, J. M. A. S. (2021). Research engagement by English language teachers in a Philippine university: Insights from a qualitative study. *Asia-Pacific Social Science Review*, 21(3).
- Thawinwong, C., & Sanrattana, W. (2022). Teachers and participatory action research for developing learning environments. *World Journal of Education*, 12(3), 17–28.
- Thorndike's trial and error theory: Learning: Psychology [Retrieved August 28, 2023, from <https://www.psychologydiscussion.net/learning/learning-theory/thorndikes-trial-and-error-theory-learning-psychology/13469>]. (2018).
- Tindowen, D. J., Guzman, J., & Macanang, D. (2019). Teachers' conception and difficulties in doing action research. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(8), 1787–1794.
- Tingabngab, V., & Binayao, B. (2023). Challenges faced by the public elementary school teachers in conducting action research. *Teacher Education and Curriculum Studies*, 8(1), 14–22.
- Tulung, J. M., Waney, M., Mailool, J., Rogahang, H. J., Weol, W., & Wuwung, O. (2022). Teachers' difficulties in implementing classroom action research: Experiences of elementary school teachers. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, 17(6), 1957–1971.
- Ulla, M. B. (2018). Benefits and challenges of doing research: Experiences from Philippine public school teachers. *Issues in Educational Research*, 28(3), 797–810.
- Ulla, M. B., Barrera, K. I. B., & Acompañado, M. M. (2017). Philippine classroom teachers as researchers: Teachers' perceptions, motivations, and challenges. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education (Online)*, 42(11), 52–64.
- Wellington, J. (2015). *Educational research: Contemporary issues and practical approaches*. Bloomsbury Publishing.